

Arsonophenyl and Sulphonamidophenyl Derivatives of Substituted Chromanones, Thiochromanones and Thiochroman 2:4-Diones

A. K. PANIGRAHI and M. K. ROUT

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3.

Received September 9, 1970

A number of 3-arsonophenyl and 3-sulphonamidophenyl derivatives of substituted 4-chromanones and 4-thiochromanones were prepared and tested for their amoebicidal and bactericidal properties.

These 4-chromanones and 4-thiochromanones were prepared by the ringclosure of β -phenoxypropionic acids and β -thiophenoxypropionic acids by polyphosphoric acid¹. The required β -phenoxypropionic acids and β -thiophenoxypropionic acids were obtained from corresponding phenols and thiophenols by condensing them with β -propiolactone in alkaline medium². 1-Dioxides of thiochromanones were prepared by treating the corresponding thiochromanone with 35% hydrogen peroxide in glacial acetic acid. Thiochroman 2:4-diones were prepared by condensing malonic acid with the corresponding thiophenol in presence of phosphorus oxychloride and anhydrous zinc chloride as the condensing agent³.

Diazotized arsanilic acid and sulphanilamide were coupled with chromanones, thiochromanones and their 1-dioxides and thiochroman 2:4-diones and the resulting azocompounds were decomposed with splitting off of nitrogen⁴⁻⁶.

Previously it has been shown that arsonophenyl- or sulphonamidophenyl group gets attached to an active methylene group, which is in α -position to an activating carbonyl group⁴⁻⁶. The reactivity of methylene group in 3-position of chromanones and thiochromanones¹ and thiochroman 2:4-diones⁷ has been well established. In light of the above evidence it has been assumed that arsonophenyl- and sulphonamidophenyl groups are attached to the 3-position of chromanones, thiochromanones and their 1-dioxides and thiochroman 2:4 diones.

EXPERIMENTAL

The arsonophenyl- and sulphonamidophenyl derivatives of chromanones, thiochromanones and their 1-dioxides and thiochroman 2:4-diones have been prepared by the usual methods as described in our previous papers⁴⁻⁶.

The analytical data of these compounds are shown in Table I.

The 3-arsonophenyl derivatives described in Table I have been screened for its anti-amoebic activity *in vitro* against a virulent strain of *Entamoeba histolytica* (Strain S T A).

The compounds on the whole show very little activity. The 3-sulphonamido derivatives are active at 10 $\mu\text{g./ml.}$ against the bacteria *S. aureus*.

TABLE I

3-Arsonophenyl- and 3-sulphonamidophenyl derivatives

No.	Nature of nucleus A	3-Arsonophenyl derivatives X = AsO ₃ H ₂		3-Sulphonamidophenyl derivatives X = SO ₂ NH ₂			
		% Arsenic		% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	4-Chromanone	21.46	21.55	10.31	10.56	4.55	4.62
2.	6-Chloro-4-chromanone	19.54	19.60	9.41	9.48	4.07	4.15
3.	6-Bromo-4-chromanone	17.42	17.57	8.31	8.37	3.60	3.67
4.	6-Methyl-4-chromanone	20.60	20.71	9.93	10.09	4.39	4.42
5.	6-Nitro-4-chromanone	18.92	19.08	9.11	9.19	7.98	8.05
6.	5 : 7-Dimethyl-4-chromanone	19.81	19.95	9.58	9.68	4.12	4.23
7.	5 : 6-Benz-4-chromanone	18.69	18.84	8.93	9.06	3.89	3.97
8.	7 : 8-Benz-4-chromanone	18.72	18.84	8.91	9.06	3.93	3.97
9.	4-Thiochromanone	20.35	20.60	19.92	20.06	4.31	4.39
10.	6-Chloro-4-thiochromanone	18.59	18.82	18.10	18.11	3.97	3.96
11.	4-Thiochromanone 1-dioxide	18.86	18.93	18.13	18.24	3.89	3.99
12.	6-Chloro-4-thiochromanone 1-dioxide	17.28	17.42	16.51	16.61	3.54	3.63
13.	Thiochroman 2,4-dione	19.63	19.85	18.89	19.23	4.17	4.21
14.	6-Chlorothiochroman 2,4-dione	18.14	18.07	17.35	17.42	3.72	3.81

The yields of the compounds were in the range of 40-65%.

The melting points of the compounds were about 300° except the 3-sulphonamido derivatives of 4-chromanone and 4-thiochromanone which decompose at 295° and 299° respectively.

The authors are grateful to Dr. Nitya Nand, Secretary, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for studying the amoebicidal and bactericidal properties and Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for providing a fellowship to one of them (A.K.P.).

REFERENCES

1. C. D. Hurd and S. Hayao, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5065.
2. T. L. Gresham, J. E. Jansen, F. W. Shaver, R. A. Bankert, W. L. Beears and Marie G. Prendergast, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 661.
3. V. R. Shah, J. L. Bose and R. C. Shah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 677.
4. A. K. Panigrahi, P. K. Jesthi and M. K. Rout, *J. & Proc. Inst. Chem.*, 1966, **38**, 175.
5. A. K. Panigrahi and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 665.
6. B. C. Mahanta, A. K. Panigrahi and M. K. Rout, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 707.
7. P. C. Rath and K. Rajagopal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 1273.